

Table 2. Mean values of breadthwise grain expansion for six generations and estimates of gene effects.^a TRRI, Aduthurai, India.

	TKM9/Pusa Basmati 1	ADT37/Pusa Basmati 1	ADT39/Pusa Basmati 1	IR50/Pusa Basmati 1	Improved White Ponni/Pusa Basmati 1
<i>Generation</i>					
P ₁	1.34 ± 0.007	1.38 ± 0.001	1.50 ± 0.005	1.57 ± 0.009	1.53 ± 0.010
P ₂	1.64 ± 0.012	1.69 ± 0.012	1.65 ± 0.013	1.64 ± 0.011	1.62 ± 0.012
F ₁	1.47 ± 0.009	1.43 ± 0.012	1.51 ± 0.010	1.60 ± 0.012	1.61 ± 0.009
F ₂	1.41 ± 0.007	1.48 ± 0.006	1.53 ± 0.007	1.59 ± 0.008	1.55 ± 0.007
BC ₁	1.41 ± 0.012	1.43 ± 0.008	1.49 ± 0.010	1.55 ± 0.008	1.54 ± 0.011
BC ₂	1.61 ± 0.013	1.61 ± 0.009	1.54 ± 0.010	1.63 ± 0.010	1.57 ± 0.009
<i>Parameter</i>					
m	1.08*±0.05	1.37*±0.04	1.62*±0.04	1.63*±0.04	1.56*±0.04
d	-0.15*±0.01	-0.15*±0.01	-0.08*±0.01	-0.03*±0.01	-0.05*±0.01
h	0.92*±0.12	0.35*±0.09	-0.27*±0.10	-0.11 ± 0.10	-0.10 ± 0.10
l	0.41*±0.04	0.16*±0.03	-0.04 ± 0.02	-0.02 ± 0.04	0.01 ± 0.04
j	-0.10*±0.04	-0.05 ± 0.03	0.03 ± 0.03	-0.08*±0.03	-0.02 ± 0.03
l	-0.53*±0.08	-0.30*±0.06	0.15*±0.07	0.09 ± 0.07	0.14*±0.07
<i>Effective factors</i>					
(d ²)/D	-	3.8	0.9	0.1	0.3
(h ²)/H	14.8	17.5	4.6	-	0.6

** = significant at the 5% level.

gene action is present, the pedigree breeding method is recommended. Dominance and epistatic interactions were also seen; selection in later

generations with one or two cycles of intermating selected segregants will result in lessening breadthwise grain expansion. ■

Inheritance of aroma in two rice crosses

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Two nonscented varieties, ADT38 and ADT39, were crossed with a scented variety, Badshabhog, to study the inheritance of aroma in rice. The parents, F₁, and F₂ were grown in Nov 1992. For each cross, 2 g of leaf blades from 15 randomly selected parent and F₁ plants and 200 F₂ plants were soaked in

10 ml of 1.7% KOH solution in test tubes and evaluated for scent after 10 min by smelling the contents.

All F₁ plants were nonaromatic, indicating the recessive nature of the gene controlling aroma (see table). A 15 nonaromatic: 1 aromatic segregation occurred for F₂ plants in both crosses, suggesting that two recessive genes control aroma in Badshabhog. Pedigree breeding with a larger population for F₂ selection is suggested for introducing scent into nonscented varieties. ■

Behavior of F₁ and F₂ populations with regard to inheritance of aroma.

Cross	Plants (no.)			χ ²	P
	Total	Nonaromatic	Aromatic		
F ₁					
ADT38/Badshabhog	15	15	-	-	-
ADT39/Badshabhog	15	15	-	-	-
F ₂					
ADT38/Badshabhog	200	189	11	0.19	0.50-0.75
ADT39/Badshabhog	200	190	10	0.53	0.25-0.50

Breeding methods

Evaluation of rice cytoplasmic male sterile lines for floral traits influencing outcrossing

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The success of hybrid rice technology depends as much on developing stable male sterility and restoration systems as on the amount of seed set on cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines by natural outcrossing. Rice is an autogamous crop; high outcrossing does not generally occur. Considerable outcrossing, however, has been reported in some wild species as a function of floral structure and biology. Environmental variation may influence the expression of these traits.

We evaluated 15 CMS lines for nine floral traits influencing outcrossing under two irrigated environments: 1991 dry season (DS) and 1991 wet season (WS). Five spikelets were randomly selected from the main panicle in each CMS line to record anther and stigma traits using stage and ocular micrometers. Anthesis duration was recorded as the time

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Routine research. Reports of screening trials of varieties, fertilizer, cropping methods, and other routine observations using standard methodologies to establish local recommendations are not ordinarily accepted.

Examples are single-season, single-trial field experiments. Field trials should be repeated across more than one season, in multiple seasons, or in more than one location as appropriate. All experiments should include replications and an internationally known check or control treatment.